

WORLD EXPERIENCE OF MARKETING SERVICES IN HOTELS, SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THEIR USE IN OUR COUNTRY

Musayeva Shoira Azimovna

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7805937>

Abstract. *In this article, the hotel industry as an economic activity is considered to provide hotel services and short-term stay in hotels, camping, motels and hostels, restaurant services, taking into account the recommendations of the World Tourism Organization on the classification of hotels.*

Keywords: *tourism, hotel, marketing services, industry, travel, hostel, strategy.*

INTRODUCTION. On the President of December 2, 2016 "On measures to ensure the rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan". The decree is significant because it aims to eliminate errors and shortcomings in the field and to develop it consistently. Therefore, in this document, the creation of favorable economic and organizational-legal conditions for the development of tourism as a strategic branch of the country's economy, the full and effective use of the potential of the regions in this direction, the fundamental improvement of the management of the sector, the creation of national tourism products and their promotion in the world markets, Directions for forming a positive tourist image of Uzbekistan have been defined. Their consistent implementation makes it possible to turn our country into one of the important centers of world tourism.

One of the main directions of tourism activity is to solve the issue of providing accommodation to tourists. Among the comprehensive services provided to tourists during the trip, the accommodation service is central and is a component of each tour.

The hospitality industry as an economic activity refers to the provision of hotel services and short-term accommodation in hotels, campsites, motels and hostels. This activity also includes restaurant services.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. When talking about the types of hotels, it is necessary to take into account the recommendations of the World Tourism Organization on the classification of hotels. This organization has developed standards for placement tools. And based on it, the following requirements are imposed on hotels:

- having more numbers than the minimum set number (usually 10) and joining a single leadership;
- provision of basic (daily room cleaning, bed making) and additional (laundry, dry cleaning, hairdressing, car rental, etc.) services;
- grouping of hotels into classes and categories based on the requirements of national standards according to the composition of services and equipment.

Austria is one of the world's recognized models of tourism. Therefore, there are more than 20 thousand hotels in the mountainous parts of the country. The cheapest means of accommodation

include no less than 100 "youth hotels" in Austria (for comparison: less than 10 in Russia). Inexpensive youth-friendly hostels are available for those who want to stay overnight, but there are no special amenities.

Austrian hotels are rated according to the 5-star system, but there are also "off-category hotels" in rural areas. They consist of one-, two-, and three-story houses, and are often opened by farming families.

3 and 5 star hotels in Austria are not much different from each other. Many hotels of this class have a swimming pool, sauna, restaurant, buffet and similar services. The similarity deepens with the decoration of hotel interiors in the "romantic style" common in Austria. In this style, modern technology is combined with the equipment of the ancient series. Sometimes, the equipment in a three-star hotel can be better than a four-star hotel (for example, for the presence of a swimming pool). In general, the hotels of the two highest categories justify their stardom with the help of a large number of rooms and a large set of services provided. Five-star hotels are distinguished by providing additional high-level service more than four-star ones.

Stars are also used to classify hotels in Egypt, but unlike the European classification, the stars are increased by about 1/2 star.

By early 1996 in China 4000 hameans of close proximity were available. The most common 5-star system is used to evaluate them. In addition, there is a specific scale in the country, according to which the simplest places of reception include "guest houses". These caravanserais or hotels can be equated with student dormitories. "Guest houses" are considered more comfortable, and these are among 2-star hotels. Hotels that meet the requirements of the more prestigious three- and four-star levels - tourist hotels, and "wine houses" can be included in the five-star level. In this regard, Chinese standards do not lag behind European standards.

England. The classification of hotels is somewhat complicated. Although some catalogs use the traditional star classification, the fronts of hotels display crowns rather than stars. To transfer the level of a hotel to a star classification in the language of crowns, one must be subtracted from the total number of crowns. For example, the Royal Norfolk Hotel in London can be listed as 3-star or 4-crown.

The most accurate classification is the classification proposed by the Association of British Travel Agencies:

- budget hotels are one-star (*) and are located in the city center and have the least amenities.
- Tourist-level hotels are two-star (**) and have a restaurant and bar.
- Mid-range hotels are three-star hotels (***). Their level of service is high enough.
- Hotels of the first level are considered four-star (****). Such hotels are designed to provide very good living conditions and excellent service.
- High-class hotels will be five-star (*****). Accommodation and service in such hotels will be at a high (extra class) level.

There are 40,000 hotels in Italy, spread throughout the country. When tourists see familiar stars at the doors of Italian hotels, their categorization is very complicated. There is no official "star" scale in the country. According to the standards accepted in Italy, hotels are divided into 3 levels.

Corresponds to 1 level - 4 star****, 2 level - 3 star***, 3 level - 2 star** hotel. In addition, each level can move freely in one direction or another.

A distinctive feature of Italian hotels is their small size (hotels with 50-80 rooms). Usually, small hotels are not included in the upper level and correspond to the 2-star level. But in resorts in the Alps, the provision and level of service are small hotels that meet the highest requirements. Some of the advantages of Italian hotels are that they have well-equipped conference rooms.

Tourist accommodation in Spain is divided into the following levels:

- Hotels of 5 levels (from 1 to 5 stars);
- hotels scale houses (from 1 to 4 stars)
- boarding houses on 3 levels.

In addition, there are state-owned enterprises that receive tourists belonging to the State Ministry of Tourism. They are mostly ancient castles, mansions, palaces located in the beautiful districts of the city and will be equipped as "Luxury" hotels.

Thus, each country has its own way of categorizing hotels, and hotels of the same level located in different countries differ greatly from each other.

The requirements for service staff in hotels can be conditionally divided into 4 groups:

1. Qualification, specialization (for all levels in hotels).

All service personnel must undergo professional training. The level of preparation should be commensurate with the services they provide. One employee should be trained to ensure the safety of hotel residents, while another employee should be qualified in the field of food safety, all of them should meet requirements such as knowledge of foreign languages.

In 1-star hotels, it is enough for reception and accommodation staff to know one foreign language.

The same is true for 2-star hotels.

3-star hotels require all staff to have sufficient knowledge of 2 foreign languages or the languages most commonly spoken by customers visiting the area.

4-star hotels have the same requirements, but they must know languages at a higher level.

In 5-star hotels, all employees must know at least 3 foreign languages and be able to communicate freely with customers.

2. Ethics, behavior. Hotel employees of all levels should know how to create a hospitable environment in the hotel, be ready to fulfill every customer's request with kindness, be calm and patient in communicating with residents.

3. Medical (medical) requirements. Employees of hotels of all levels must undergo periodic medical examinations and receive relevant certificates.

4. Uniform. Hotel staff of all levels who communicate with customers must always wear uniforms, uniforms must always be clean and well-groomed, and each employee must wear a personal badge with his name and surname written on it.

All hotel complexes must have special conditions for employees to rest and eat. The size of these conditions should correspond to the number of employees.

Our hotels must also meet the level of these world standards, because for the development of tourism, it is necessary to receive tourists from all corners of the world, from all classes and categories. These require proper conditions. Only then it is possible to increase the number of foreign tourists.

REFERENCES

1. On measures related to the rapid development of the tourism network" Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 5, 2019 No. PQ-4095.
2. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4755 dated June 19, 2020 "On additional measures to develop the tourism sector in strict compliance with the requirements of the enhanced sanitary and epidemiological safety regime".
3. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-5249 dated September 22, 2021 "On financial support for activities to be implemented in order to further accelerate large-scale construction and beautification works in Samarkand region and increase tourism potential."
4. Alexandrova A.Yu. International tourism. - M.: Aspect press, 2016. - 470 p.
5. Alimov R., Kamilova M., Kurbanova D. Cluster concept of economic development: theory and practice. - T.: Institut ekonomiki AN Ruz., 2005. - P. 36.
6. Alieva MT, Umurzhanov A. Economy of tourist countries. - T.: Economy - Finance, 2005. - 339 p.
7. Babkin AV Special tourism. - Rostov-on-Don: Phoenix, 2008. - 252 p.
8. Balabanov IT, Balabanov AI Economic tourism. Uchebnoe posobie. - M.: Finance and statistics, 2003. - 176 p.
9. Balabanov IT Economic tourism / IT Balabanov, AI Balabanov - M.: Finance and statistics, 2002. - S. 25.
10. Birzhakov MB Introduction to tourism. – Izdanie 9-e pererabotannoe i dopolnennoe. - SPb.: Izdatelsky dom Gerda, 2007. - 576 p.
11. MS Azimovna Improving The Study Of Consumer Behavior *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 109
12. S Musayeva WAYS TO IMPROVE DEMAND FORMATION AND SALES PROMOTION AT GOLDEN OIL LLC *Science and innovation 1 (A5)*, 215-220
13. MS Azimovna Development of innovative marketing strategies in agriculture. *Web of Scientist: International Journal of Scientific Research 3 (02)*, 538-544
14. MS Azimovna, RN Ulugbekovna Development Conditions and Modern Trends of Business Tourism Worldwide *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BUSINESS DIPLOMACY AND ECONOMY 2 (2)*, 63-66
15. MS Azimovna THE MAIN RESULTS OF THE LABOR PRODUCTIVITY OF THE STAFF OF THE HOTEL "BILLURI SITORA" LLC. *Galaxy International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research 11(1)*, 348-352
16. MS Azimovna THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF MARKETING TOOLS IN INCREASING THE INTERNATIONAL COMPETITIVENESS OF THE TEXTILE ENTERPRISE *Science and Innovation 2 (1)*, 47-53
17. S Musayeva MECHANISMS OF FUNCTIONING OF LOGISTIC STRUCTURES *Science and innovation 2 (A2)*, 196-202
18. S Musayeva WAYS TO IMPROVE THE POLICY OF DISTRIBUTION OF GOODS IN FURNITURE PRODUCTION ENTERPRISES *Science and innovation 2 (A2)*, 152-156
19. S Musayeva IN THE CONDITIONS OF MODERNIZATION IN UZBEKISTAN THE NEED TO EVALUATE ENTERPRISES *Science and innovation 2 (A2)*, 35-40

20. MS Azimovna Ways to Improve the Use of Marketing Information in the Assessment of "Stekloplastik" LLC American Journal of Economics and Business Management 5 (11), 338-343
21. MS Azimovna Efficiency of advertising activities of trading organizations and ways to increase IT Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities 12 (3), 93-97
22. Usmanov IA, Musayeva Sh.A. Features of marketing activities in the construction industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan. NOVATEUR PUBLICATIONS Journal NX- A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal ISSN No: 2581 - 4230 VOLUME 7, ISSUE 1, Jan. -2021 <https://repo.journalnx.com/index.php/nx/article/view/793>
23. Usmanov I.A. Musaeva Sh.A. Features of marketing organization in the market of construction services. Service. Scientific journal. - Samarkand. No. 2, 2021 - pp. 86-90.
24. Usmanov IA Study of the Provision of Construction Facilities with Management Personnel. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ON ORANGE TECHNOLOGY. Volume: 03 Issue: 9 | Sep 2021. p.31-33 <https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJOT/article/view/2171>
25. Usmanov IA, Jumanov Sh.N. Ways to improve quality control of construction and installation works. Oriental renaissance: innovative, educational, natural and social sciences scientific journal. ISSN 2181-1784. Volume 1, Issue 10. November 2021. – P. 651-658 <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ways-to-improve-quality-control-of-construction-and-installation-works>
26. Usmanov I.A. Buriev H.T. A development strategy for the construction industry in Uzbekistan: organizational aspects of implementation. International scientific and technical journal. Real estate: economy, administration. Moscow, MGSU- No. 4 / 2021